

Review

Advanced Research Progress of Food Drying Technology

**Shamim Hossan^{1*}, Sazzadul Wasim², Mst Nushrat Yiasmin¹, Md. Nazmus Saqib³,
Md. Easdani^{1,4}, Siyuan Liu¹**

¹School State Key Laboratory of Food Science and Resources, School of Food Science and Technology, National Engineering Research Center for Functional Food, International Joint Research Laboratory for Lipid Nutrition and Safety, Collaborative Innovation Center of Food Safety and Quality Control in Jiangsu Province, Jiangnan University, China

²Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh-2202, Bangladesh

³Department of Nutrition & Food Engineering, Daffodil International University, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh

⁴Department of Food Engineering and Technology, South Purbachal, Kanchan, Dhaka-1461, Bangladesh

Abstract: This comprehensive review examines the historical progression of food drying methods, encompassing traditional practices like sun and air drying and their evolution into modern techniques that prioritize retaining nutritional value during the drying process. A wide spectrum of drying methodologies is addressed, ranging from conventional sun drying to advanced approaches such as tunnel, spray, drum, freeze, microwave, and fluidized bed drying, each playing a vital role in preserving diverse food items. The study also investigates the impact of pretreatment procedures on different drying technologies, including solar, greenhouse solar, and hybrid solar dryers, alongside emerging methods like Electro Hydrodynamic (EHD) and Pulsed Electric Field (PEF) drying, as well as ultrasound-assisted drying. The underlying principles governing these techniques, such as model drying, impingement drying, high electric field drying, and electro-hydrodynamic drying, are analyzed comprehensively. Through a critical evaluation of recent developments in food drying within the context of food processing technology, this review offers valuable insights into the potential applications of these methods for enhancing food preservation while retaining optimal nutritional profiles.

Keywords: Food drying technology, solar drying, electro hydro dynamic-EHD, pulsating electric field, and ultrasound drying technology

*Corresponding Author

Phone: +8613275102818

Email Address: shamim96.ft@gmail.com (Shamim Hossan)

Accepted: 17 September, 2023; **Published:** 7 October, 2023

How to cite this article: Shamim Hossan, Sazzadul Wasim, Mst Nushrat Yiasmin, Md. Nazmus Saqib, Md. Easdani, Siyuan Liu (2023).

Advanced Research Progress of Food Drying Technology. North American Academic Research, 6(9), 18-47. doi:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8415214>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

It might be dried to preserve a product's quality, which involves removing moisture by evaporation or condensation. Drying agricultural products to eliminate as much moisture as possible while retaining their active nutrients allows them to be securely stored for a long time. Drying concentrates food without compromising its tissue, healthiness, or aesthetic appeal by removing large amounts of free water. Heat and mass are transferred within the material as the fabric dries [1]. Some old methods, such as Sun-drying, Tunnel drying, Spray drying, Drum drying, Freeze-drying, Microwave drying, and Fluidized-bed drying, a process of removing water [2]–[7] These methods have the advantage of saving both money and energy. These techniques are still used today since they have been considered more affordable and effective because they utilize unrestricted natural power.

Additionally, drying typically takes a long time and permits significant nutrient and bioactive compound degradation. Various initiatives have been made to create drying methods that would lower moisture content, lessen bioactive component deterioration brought on by biochemical changes, and reduce nutritional value while drying [8]. The development of drying technology in the last few decades has been very rapid, for example- solar dryers, Greenhouse solar dryers, Hybrid solar dryers, Electro hydrodynamic (EHD), Pulsed electric field-PEF, and ultrasound. Each approach has unique concepts, workings, advantages, and drawbacks. This review aims to learn more about the drying techniques used in food processing, including traditional and contemporary types. Preserving various crops is an area of growing interest for the agricultural sector.

This study comprehensively illustrates the approaches to food preservation, considering sun drying as the earliest method of natural conservation. Food storage techniques date back to 12000 B.C. (Before Christ). The earliest preservation technique was sun drying, which was most popular in the ancient era. Stated the food was dried by placing the things outside in the sun. People at the time preserved food by solar dehydrating, but this didn't ensure that the food would remain of high quality over time. This process was entirely dependent on nature, which could not offer an efficient means of food preservation. One of the oldest techniques for food preservation was used by early humans. It was first used to dry large amounts of food and vegetables in the arid and semi-arid regions around 12,000 B.C. [9].

In some regions of the globe, the method is still in use, but in others, more practical and pleasant techniques, like the dehydration method, have taken their place. It entails laying food products out in the sunshine so that the heat from the sun will cause the water content to evaporate. Due to the removal of up to 80% of the wetness, bacterial development is prevented. A fifth of the initial weight and up to 50% less space is also achieved. The primary benefit of this method of food storage is that it only needs sunlight, making it affordable.

Contrary to contemporary techniques, the food did not dry evenly and kept moisture, a drawback to the entire process. In addition, it was time-consuming and cumbersome, ruined food flavor, and wasn't ecologically favorable. Other disadvantages include the lengthy drying times required for the goods and the near impossibility of using them in unfavorable weather or environmental conditions, among other things[2].

2. Fundamentals of food drying

During this process, food is dried by converting the water's original state vapor. After that, take it out of the food so that it can lose moisture. Drying is a dehydration procedure that uses heat from heated air or sun energy to remove water from food items. To avoid compromising the standard of the final product, water must be removed as quickly as possible [10]. The drying procedure was created to make the best possible use of energy sources and basic materials [11]. Conduction, convection, and radiation are all methods of heat transmission that can be used during drying, except freeze-drying, to force water to vaporize. In the interim, vapor elimination is encouraged using the air [12].

3. Technology for Drying Food Products

3.1 Sun-drying

Fruits can be dried in the sun without risk due to their large sugar and acid content. The drying of livestock and vegetables in the weather is not advised. Acid and sugar content are minimal in vegetables. This makes food

deterioration more likely. When temperature and humidity are not regulated, meats with a high protein content are the best food for bacteria growth [2]. Using the sun's energy directly, agricultural goods can be dried by solar drying [8]. The benefit of this technique is that it saves money and energy. However, it relies on renewable electricity and is incredibly susceptible to unpredictable weather changes [13]. The sun-drying technique is typically used in equatorial regions with at least 6 hours of sunshine and radiation levels of up to 500–800 W/m² per hour, which equals 185 W/m² per day [14]. Peppers are dried using consistent surface contact with the sun, lasting up to a week. The range is from 20 to 37 °C [15]. The moisture content of mango and wild bean foliage decreased by up to 10-15% when dried in full sunlight [16].

Products	Characteristics	References
Shrimp	Astaxanthin substantially reduced, and cholesterol oxidation products increased during drying	[17]
Takuan-zuke (pickled daikon)	Compared to salt-pressing, the amount of secondary metabolites increases	[18]
Chitosans	without the use of whitening chemicals, high-viscosity white chitosan can be produced	[19]
Brown rice in germination	The overall amount of polyphenols and antioxidants, as well as -oryzanol activity, are all increased by sun drying	[20]
Red pepper	To achieve 24.24% of the moisture level, solar hybrid greenhouse drying (active) takes 12 hours, and open-air sun drying takes 24 hours	[21]
Grapes	Indirect sunlight drying requires 120 hours, whereas exposed sun drying requires 201 hours to reduce water content from 79.8% (wb) to 20.2% (wb)	[3]

Table 1: The characteristics of sun-dried food items in different experiments

3.2 Tunnel drying

The tunnel dryer travels through the transparent flat collection plate using four DC fans in sequence while receiving direct thermal energy [22]. In the commercial setting, it is frequently used to dry seafood and agricultural goods. Solar heat energy is used in tube dryers. It is more efficient than solar drying but unpredictable because it depends on the weather [[23]. The grapes are dried in a tunnel dryer at a temperature of 10-28 °C in good weather, and a covered tunnel

dryer with a 200 μm thick semi-transparent polyethylene sheet is used. After drying, the wine will hit 16% of the moisture web[24]. Fish salted for 16 hours is first dried using a tube dryer. The procedure will be completed when the fish's water content falls to 16.78% web. The voltage applied is increased incrementally from 7.0 to 14.0 V [22]

Name of the Products	Characteristics	References
Tomato	In 10 hours, the water level dropped from 91% (web) to 7.1% (web)	[25]
Chilli	Reduces moisture level for 20 hours by up to 98.25 percent	[26]
Grape	For seven days, the water level dropped by up to 16%	[24]
Pulp Aonla	After 16 dehydrating hours, the water level dropped from 424.93% (db.) to 10.08% (db.)	[27]
Leaves of fenugreek	Reduced water level for 17 hours, from 89% (web) to 9% (web)	[28]
Mango	In 9.5 hours, the water level dropped from 85.5% (web) to 12.0% (web)	[29]

Table 2: The characteristics of tunnel-dried food items in different experiments

Fig. 1: a. Direct solar dryer [1], [30] b. Solar cabinet dryer [30] c. Indirect solar dryer [1] d. Mixed-type solar dryer [1] e. Modified mixed-type solar dryer [31] f. Mixed-mode solar dryer with forced convection [32] g. Hybrid solar dryer [33] h. Electro-hydrodynamic apparatus [34] i. Ultrasound drying [35], [36] j. Mechanism of Ultrasound drying [35], [36].

3.3 Spray drying

Spray drying is frequently employed in culinary heat-sensitive processes [37]. Compared to the freeze-drying technique, this procedure uses less specific energy [38].

Name of the Products	Characteristics	Carrier	References
Blueberry juice	Maltodextrin maintains more potent antioxidant activity than inulin.	Inulin and maltodextrin	[39]

Strawberry	The least amount of wetness is present in particles created by spray drying. It has turned out to be the most effective way to encapsulate strawberry taste	Gum Arabic, β and γ cyclodextrins, maltodextrins, modified polysaccharides, and xanthan gum	[40]
Curcumin	highly effective against human HepG2 carcinoma cells	Isolated soy protein	[41]
Curcumin	Inulin is less resistant to acidity than modified starch made from modified starch using microencapsulation methods. Due to its more effective coating ability, inulin performs better in fizzy beverages.	Gelatin, tamarin gum, pectin, β -cyclodextrin, modified starch, inulin, and maltodextrin	[42]
Fish oil	Methanol and fish oil microparticles demonstrated the most remarkable oil durability during storing.	HPC (hydroxypropyl cellulose)	[43]

Table 3: lists the traits of food products spray-dried in different foods

Spray drying turns a liquid, emulsion, or suspension substance into a solid product. The atomizer will constantly send the spray drying principle into the chamber, where it will be split into tiny droplets. Most of the solvent in the created droplets will vaporize when they come into touch with heated air through convection, forming a powder particle [44]. The benefits of spray drying include a quick drying time and comparatively low operating expenses. However, because a high temperature is used in this drying technique, dehydrating food that contains protein, like egg white, will degrade the protein's quality [37]. Because it is quicker, more adaptable, less expensive, and creates food microparticles of high quality, spray drying is frequently used in encapsulation. According to Lucas et al. [45], spray drying the oleoresin turmeric curcumin stabilizes the product and extends its storage life. Spray drying was used by Liu et al. [37] to create a hydrolyzed ovalbumin formulation that exhibited emulsifying activity, increased protein solubility, and foaming capability. In their study, Hoskin et al. [46], dried blueberry pomace that contained flavonoids using a spray technique. Blueberry-polyphenol foods with biological activity and phytochemical antioxidants were made using spray drying.

3.4 Drum drying

A heated cylinder constantly spins when drum drying is taking place. Drum dryers have a high drying efficiency and cheap running expenses, with a heat energy efficacy of 60–90% [16]. During use, the substance is supplied to the rotating drum's exterior surface as a liquid, slurry, or dried dough to create a thin coating that covers the drum surface and is

between 0.5 and 2.0 millimeters thick. The drum's interior is heated by vapor, which causes the top temperature to be extremely high. Condensate gas raises the temperature and warms the slurry via conduction through the cylinder wall. The pace at which a cylinder rotates affects how long it takes to dry [4].

Name of the Products	Characteristics	References
Skim milk	Lysine levels dropped after 40 seconds of drying at an average temperature of 115 °C	[47]
Apple skin	Polyphenols are degraded	[16]
Peeled pomegranate	Hydrolyzed tannic concentration is retained during drum drying at 100-110°C	[48]
Rice berry flour	Rice berry flour can be pregelatinized using drum drying	[49]
Rye	Effective in reducing Fusarium culmorum, which produces deoxynivalenol, nivalenol, and zearalenone	[50]
Red cabbage	High anthocyanin efficacy packaging is a possibility	[51]

Table 4: lists the traits of food products that have been drum-dried in different experiments

During the drying process, the complete area of the disc actuator experiences heat transfer [16],[52] The temperature and water content of a thin sheet of material affixed to the heated drum's surface will quickly rise, simultaneously cooking and drying the material. Drum drying is ideal for most heat-sensitive goods because only brief periods are subjected to high temperatures [16], [53]. Powdered milk, cereals, apple sauce, fruit puree, fruit powder, dry stews, infant food, and other food items are among the things that can be drum-dried. Potato flour can also be dried using this device [54]. The starch granule structure is broken down during this dehydrating process, enhancing product solubility and water uptake. Additionally, skim milk powder is produced using dehydrating machines. Aalaei et al.'s study on drum-drying skim milk powder [47] revealed more significant lysine losses than freeze-drying. It's a disadvantage of the drum-drying process. To ascertain the rates of total polyphenol content in apple skin deterioration, Henriquez et al. [16] dried the apple skin. In addition, Olsen et al. [15] drum-dried high-water pomace fruits and veggies.

Drying Method	Mechanism of Drying Method	Advantages	Disadvantages	Reference
Sun Drying	Utilizes solar energy to evaporate moisture	- Cost-effective -Environmentally friendly	- Weather-dependent -limitation to control the drying process and parameter	[55]

			- Chance of contamination with foreign materials and infestation	
Spray Drying	Converts liquid, emulsion, or suspension into a solid	- Continuous Operation - Fully controllable operation - heat sensitive products can be fed	- High feed rate is required to pump to the atomizer - High capital cost - limited versatility in producing particles or structures	[56], [57]
Tunnel Drying	Utilizes direct thermal energy with the assistance of fans in a tunnel-like structure	- Efficient drying process	- Dependence on weather conditions for solar heat energy utilization	[58]
Drum Drying	Heated cylinder continuously spins to evaporate moisture	- High drying efficiency - Convenient for slurry drying	- Breakdown of starch granule structure during drying - Difficulties in removal of products which shows thermal plasticity.	[59], [60]
Freeze Drying	Sublimates moisture from the frozen material using low temperatures and vacuum pressure	- Preserves Oxidizable components	- High Capital Cost - High energy usage and operating costs	[61]–[63]
Microwave Drying	Utilizes microwave radiation to heat the water in the material and evaporate moisture	- Rapid drying process	- Cannot be a singular drying operation device - Uneven distribution of microwave field can occur	[64]–[66]
Fluidized-Bed Drying	Uses a fluidized column, airflow, and heating to create a fluidized bed for efficient drying of	- high thermal efficiency - high drying rate	- Both nutritional and sensory quality declines	[67]

various
materials

Table 5: Comparison among different types of dryers

3.5 Freeze-drying

After being chilled, water is sublimated through the process of freeze-drying. Dry products are frequently created by preserving their bioactive components in the food and medicinal industries [5] Another name for freeze-drying is lyophilization. The process has three steps: chilling, primary, and secondary. Low temps are used to process the components until they are frozen. Sublimation is the main concept of drying. Ice melts straight into vapor through sublimation, a direct transition from solid to gas without first entering the liquid phase. Therefore, the desiccated product must be less than or close to the equilibrium vapor pressure of the frozen liquid, which can be accomplished using a vacuum pump [68]. To retain water in the freezing phase, the primary drying step must be at -10°C or less and 2 mmHg absolute pressure or less [69]. Water shrinks from the top layer when it sublimates and is left behind as a permeable, desiccated product. While vapor is carried through the porous layers of the dry matter, latent heat from sublimation is transmitted through the dry and frozen layers. No more frozen layer is eliminated at the conclusion of freeze-drying, leaving no more area for sublimation [70].

The release concept is used for secondary drying. Desorption is the process of eliminating non-frozen water, also referred to as bound water. After initial drying is complete, secondary drying begins. The holes in the dry materials are used to convey the desorbed water vapor [68]. The most significant moisture content reduction is the goal of this step. It offers durability because the result still has 10 to 35% bound water after the sublimation process. The crucial secondary drying component is the equilibrium between the adsorption and release of moisture in porous media. To obtain outstanding product quality, the temperature and moisture level must be managed [71]. The characteristics of the products created are altered when freeze-drying is used on a variety of food items. Bioactive chemicals, fragrance, shrinkage, and rehydration of the product are some of the elements that change during the process [72]

Name of the Products	Characteristics	References
Watermelon, mango	Ascorbic acid levels did not alter significantly, but β-carotene and phenolic substances did	[73]
Orange Puree	able to keep nutrients while having a crunchy texture, particularly in terms of vitamin C and β-carotene	[74]
Starch hydrogel	The homogeneous, solid structure of starch gel is reduced during freeze-drying. Gel with a high amylose content withstands dehydration damage	[75]

Citrus by-product extracts	For encapsulating citrus by-product extracts, the freeze-drier moisture content is lower than the dryer spray moisture content. With the properties of permeable particles, crystallinity is also common	[76]
Garlic	The pretreatment cycle of freeze-thawing before freeze-drying shortens the drying process and saves energy while also enhancing the temperature stability and product quality of garlic	[77]

Table 6: The characteristics of freeze-dried food items in different research

Free-drying has advantages because it can reduce the loss of volatile compounds, minerals susceptible to heat, and aroma compounds. To limit changes in food's properties, the low temperature used for preservation inhibits microbial development and enzymatic reactions. This method can eliminate 95.0 to 99.5% of the water. Additionally, this technique shields oxidizable substances because vacuum pressure is used. Aseptic freeze-drying can keep products sterile and contaminant-free throughout the entire process. Cost is one of the most significant barriers preventing the business from using freeze-drying. One of the most costly operating systems for producing dry foods is freeze drying, which has high energy usage and higher operating and upkeep costs. The high vacuum pressure can also eliminate some volatile substances, another drawback. The assurance of sterility in the drying area and the procedure for bringing the containers inside have several issues [4]

3.6 Microwave drying

Microwaves are electromagnetic radiation with a frequency range of 0.3 GHz to 3.0 GHz and a 1 mm to 1 m wavelength. The range of these wavelengths exceeds that of radio radiation. The microwave permeates the food, heating the water that is present there. It raises the difference in vapor pressure between the product's core and its surface, enabling moisture to be quickly transferred out of the material [4], [6] Heat is produced by microwave-to-medium contact. Heat is produced by the mass dissipation and conversion of electromagnetic energy. The method used to transform this energy type relies on the properties of the medium and the wave frequency [78]. The chamber retains microwave radiation after cooling or heating.

Name of the products	Characteristics	References
Turmeric	Has an impact on the amount and purity of curcumin in essential oils	[79]
Cocoa pod husks	Boost bioactive substance production and antioxidant activity	[80]

Cranberries	High fruit antioxidant activity is produced by increasing the reactive cranberry compounds	[81]
Persimmon chips	It has the highest sensory chip value, can enhance rehydration, and can maintain color and texture	[82]
Balsam pears	While minimizing burnt fragrance, microwave drying may preserve standard flavor	[83]

Table 7: The characteristics of microwave-dried food products in different experiments

The cavity substance usually captures energy because of how little heat is lost through convection. In main, the water in the substance absorbs this energy, raising its temperature, evaporating some of its water, and reducing its hydration content [84] At 2450 MHz, microwave appliances used for food are used (12.24 cm wavelength). Food's water, fat, and sugar compounds capture microwave radiation energy by heating the dielectric. Since most water molecules are electric dipoles, they are charged positively and negatively. They spin to adapt to the shifting electrical fields brought on by microwave radiation. This molecule's motion will produce heat from spinning molecules slamming into one another. Because there are fewer dipole moments in lipids, sugars, and ice, the molecules spin more forcefully during microwave drying [84]. In its implementation, microwave drying cannot be a singular drying operation device.

Other drying processes like heated air, suction, and multi-flash dryers must be used in conjunction [85] Also possible is its combination with freeze drying (Microwave-free drying) [72]. Microwaves are frequently used for cooking vegetables. According to reports, this way of drying carrots produced the total solids, dried them quickly, and maintained considerably more shrinkage than heat and infrared drying techniques. Materials were better shielded from staining by microwave drying [86]. Rice, sugar cane, grain, and cotton biomass surfaces are said to be damaged by microwave drying, which releases numerous volatile chemicals and reduces the capacity of rice stems, sugar cane, and grain to crystallize [87].

Fluidized-bed drying method

The different drying methods created have successfully delivered consistent moisture content for drying outcomes and sped up the process. Drying in a fluidized bed is one such method. Fluidized bed dryers guarantee high heat output, mass transfer, and improved drying rates for particular food drying[7]. The dryer comprises a fluidized column, an airflow fan, and electrical heating and temperature regulation [88]. The substance that needs to dry is spread out throughout the drier. The product is pushed to dry by hot air with some volume and pressure as its weight decreases. Fluidized bed dryers are frequently used to dry moist particulates, fluidizable granular materials, slurries, and pastes [89].

Name of the products	Characteristics	References
Shelled corn	While the moisture content of the solids rises with an increase in the mass flow rate of dry solids, it reduces with an increase in the temperature of the incoming air	[90]

Soybean kernels	At greater drying temperatures, air speeds, and drying times, the proportion of cracked increased	[91]
Brown algae (Ascophyllum nodosum)	Compared to other dehydration techniques, it offers a higher output overall	[92]
Paddy	Rice quality is unaffected by using intake air temperatures between 40 and 150 °C. Also well maintained is the grade of rice milled	[93]
Citrus sinensis Peels	In comparison to solar drying, fluidized bed drying can better preserve vitamin C and limonene content. Additionally, it can decrease microbial development, extending storage life	[94]

Table 8: The characteristics of fluidized-bed dried food items from different experiments

Various fruits, veggies, grains, and farm goods like rice and maize are dried using the fluidized bed drying technique. Its advantages include mixing solid materials, effective mass and heat transmission, quick and affordable drying, simple control, uniform temperature, and convenient material handling and transfer. While product quality, such as color, structure, taste, and nutritional components, is declining, the absence of energy efficiency is less than 50% [12],[88].

4. Food and agricultural products of Solar drying technology

4.1 Solar dryers

Simple machines known as solar dryers capture solar radiation and transmit it as thermal energy. The object receives this thermal energy to dehydrate it. Solar dryers can raise the temperature at which moisture is lost and lower the relative humidity, reducing the moisture content of desiccated goods. Solar dryers, instead of sun dehydration, have a special construction that controls dehydration and shields the product from harm from insects, weather, and dust [95], [96]. The quality of the products dried through solar dehydration is superior to that of the sun-dehydrated products because the products are protected, and the dehydration time is significantly shortened [97], [98]. Solar dryers can be categorized based on thermal techniques or operational systems (Fig. 2). The different types of solar dryers are direct dryers, indirect dryers, mixed-type dryers, greenhouse solar dryers, and hybrid solar dryers with energy storage devices.

Fig. 2: solar dryers Classification [1]

4.2 Direct solar dryers

The traditional method for dehydrating crops and food items is direct sun dehydration. A transparent cover is used in this sun-drying method to prevent heat loss and shield the food substance from wind and precipitation [99][100].

Working principle of direct solar dryers

Fig. 1(a) illustrates the fundamentals of the direct sun drying strategy. The transparent cover reflects some solar energy, while the remainder is transferred inside the box dryer. Furthermore, the food surface shows the quantity of solar energy. The substance dehydrates as the material's temperature rises. The air pushed into the chamber drier removes the moisture from the food-related materials [101].

4.3 Solar cabinet dryer

Hallak et al. [30] showed an adjusted solar cabinet drier, as seen in **Fig. 1(b)**. The drying room of the dryer, which was constructed from a metal stairway, was topped by a dehydrating chimney. The dryer's capacity was appropriate for drying 20 kg of agricultural produce. In the meantime, Gbaha et al. [102] developed a direct solar dryer for drying crops like cassava, banana, and mango. They demonstrated that the dryer's thermal performance is superior to dehydration by the sun's natural radiation. A direct sun dryer was developed by Eke and Arinze [103]. The maize's original moisture level was decreased by drying from 29 to 12%. (web). A direct drier cut the dehydrating period by 55% compared to natural solar dehydration. Direct solar dehydration had a drying efficacy of 45.6%, compared to natural open-sun dehydration's 22.7%. Seveda and Jhahharia [104] created a direct sun drier to dry cardamom. At a temperature of 55.7°C, the cardamom's initial moisture level of 75.6% dropped to 10.1%. Comparing the solar dryer to open-air dehydration naturally, the dehydration period was decreased by 55%.

A solar tunnel drier with a storage substance was evaluated by Ayyappan and Mayilsamy [105] for heating and dehydrating air. In their trial, they applied the dehydrating system under two different conditions: with the heat storage material for heating air and without it, and found that the moisture content of copra decreased from 52 to 7.1% (w. b) at a dehydration period of 52 and 78 h. The dryer's heat efficacy was 15%. Using the heat storage substance, the dryer's effectiveness improved by 2% to 3%. The effectiveness and dehydrating properties of various drier types, including direct and indirect solar dryers, were studied by Sanusi et al. [106]. They discovered that the tomato moisture content and air temperature differential are greater in indirect solar dryers than in oblique solar driers. Tefera et al. [107]

examined the effectiveness of various direct drier types (wooden and pyramid). They found that the time needed to dehydrate potatoes was reduced by 2-3 hours compared to drying under the sun naturally.

Additionally, the wooden shape and the pyramid's drier form do not work. Eke [108] constructed a straight solar dryer using natural convection. Various veggies with a constant slicing thickness of 15 millimeters, including tomato, okra, and carrot, were assessed. According to the statistics, compared to dehydration caused by exposure to heat, dehydration time was cut in half with an air-dehydrating temperature of 60 °C.

4.4 Indirect solar dryers

The secondary way of solar dehydration is more effective than the direct technique. In this method, a flat plate absorber heats the surrounding air through indirect solar dehydration. According to the method used to move the air over the food, forced convection and natural convection systems are the two categories under which indirect solar dryers fall. Foods are dried using indirect solar dryers to avoid direct solar radiation. Low temps are necessary for the quality of the substance. The drawbacks of natural solar dehydration are lessened when an indirect solar dehydration device is used [109], [110].

Working principle of indirect solar dryers

The concept behind the indirect solar dehydration technique is shown in **Figure 1(c)**. Solar Energy is collected using a solar collector air warmer. A dehydrating container is connected to the atmosphere warmer. Foods can circulate in the dehydrating compartment as heated air from the solar heater enters [111]–[114]. The farm produce is arranged in indirect dryers on plates or shelves inside an opaque dehydrating cabinet. A separate device known as the solar collector is used to heat the air in the cupboard. The quantity of ventilation through the collection determines how effectively indirect solar dryers work, and this airflow can be increased by using a fan. The fan can keep the necessary ventilation rate in the dehydrating compartment, resulting in the material's constant loss of moisture [110], [115], [116].

4.5 Mixed-type solar dryers

Mixed-mode sun drying combines the use of two techniques. (Direct and indirect solar dehydration). In mixed-mode solar dehydration, the food can be dried using heated air from a dryer and direct solar energy [1].

Working principle of mixed-mode solar dryers

In mixed-mode dryers, the food that needs to be dried is heated using two methods: absorbing solar energy directly and heating the surrounding air in the solar collection. **Fig. 1(d)** depicts the mixed-mode solar dryer's working theory. The transparent solar heating cover lets solar energy enter, warming the surrounding air. Because mixed-mode sun dryers boost the temperature and air movement rate at which food is produced, the dehydration rate increases [117], [118].

Previous studies on mixed-mode solar dryers

A mixed-type solar dryer was created by Exell and Kornsakoo [31] for dehydrating cereals. **Fig. 1(e)** shows the dryer's configuration. The dryer had three primary components: a chimney, a paddy room, and a solar collection. In the solar collection, a dark substance was elevated above the surface. Burnt husk and a piece of transparent polyethylene plastic were used to make the absorption substance. A mixed-type solar dryer was investigated by Wibulsawas and Thaina [119]. The drying room was 1.04 by 0.75 by 1.03 meters in size. The sun collection was situated at 14° and measured 1.04 by 1.8 meters. Glass, acrylic, and fiber-reinforced plastic were all used as clear shields for solar air collectors. The two absorption surfaces that the experts tested were (a) a black-painted mild steel plate and (b) a black metal lathe frame. The metal sheet and glass top displayed the most incredible dehydrating performance. Simate [120] developed the thin-layer algebraic model for a mixed drier. The indirect dryer's collection was 3.34 m long, while the mixed-type sun dryers were 1.8 m long and could hold 90 kg of maize grain. The indirect dryer's drying expense was 16.05 US\$/ton, whereas the mixed-mode dryer was 12.76 US\$/ton.

Rice kernels were dried using a mixed-mode dryer, according to Zomorodian et al. [121]. The results demonstrated that the mixed-mode dryer efficiently dehydrates grains and removes water while providing significant data. The rice

kernels were dried with a dryer that had a 21.24% efficiency, using an average of 6-8% energy. In the meantime, Bukola and Olalusi [118] assessed and computed the efficiency of a mixed-type dryer. The dehydrating air temperature in the dryer increased up to 74%. The dehydrating rate was 0.62 kg/h, and the dehydrating efficiency was 57.5%. Pardhi and Bhagoria [32] studied a mixed dryer by applying smooth and rough plate solar collectors in Fig. 1(f). The air temperature of the solar collector increased to 69.2°C without load, and the dehydrating air temperature in the dehydrating chamber was 64.1°C. Grapes with a mass of 3 kg were dried from a primary moisture content of 81.4% to a final moisture content of 18.6% within 4 days of dehydrating time, whereas natural-sun dehydration took 8 days.

5. Greenhouse solar dryers

The greenhouse dryer system is the best method for preserving different types of agricultural (fruits, veggies, and grains) and culinary items. The greenhouse solar structure is a sun collector that allows for year-round, efficient treatment, dehydration, or plant production operations. A lot of study has been done to enhance the effectiveness of the greenhouse method[122]. Greenhouses can operate passively or actively [112]. The categorization of greenhouse sun dryers is shown in Fig. 3.

A parabolic formed (PV) aerated greenhouse dryer for drying fresh chiles through a dark substance was manufactured by Janjai et al. [123]. The 44 m² laundry floors were covered in polycarbonate panels. On a sunny day at midday, the dryer's interior air temperature was 65°C. Although the air inside the dryer was hot, it was not very damp. The concrete floor's heat storage lessened the difference in the drying air temperature. Less time was required to dehydrate chilies (weighing 100–150 kg) in the greenhouse dryer than in the open weather

Fig. 3: The classification of greenhouse solar dryer[1]

Sethi and Arora added a motivated north wall to a garden dryer [124]. The disposition angle on the north side was increased for the tray with a defined breadth. Slices of bitter gourd were dried using a dryer with and without a driven north side. Dehydration took place in both spontaneous and forced modes. A UV-steadied polyethylene covering spanned the dryer floor's 6 x 4 m section. The adoption of the inspired north side resulted in a reduction in the overall dehydration time of about 13.13 percent. 16.6% of forced flow was employed.

To dry okra, Adu et al. [125] developed and built 10 greenhouse dryers in Nigeria. The dehydrating collection had two sides that were completely covered in dark material and the remaining two sides that were only partially covered. Translucent polyethylene was used to cover the ceiling. Okra's original moisture content, which was 86% at an air-dehydrating temperature of about 50°C, dropped to 3% after 23 hours. Almuhanha [126] built a garden dryer in Saudi

Arabia to dry dates. The fiberglass-covered, 2 × 1 × 1 m aluminum-framed building had a roof at a 30° inclination. The two drier receptacles were 0.3 × 1 × 1 meters. The necessary ventilation was maintained by a fan that was set. During the dehydration procedure, the daily average heat effectiveness was 60.11 percent.

6. Hybrid solar dryers

Through storing thermal energy, dehydration occurs continuously during the hours of sunlight in a combination solar dryer. Dehydration constantly proceeds, and the microbe infection prevents food from potentially degrading. Due to the abundance of solar radiation and the rising expense of fossil fuels, solar-assisted dehydrating devices are widely used to dehydrate agricultural and food items in many emerging nations. Due to its heat sources, a hybrid sun dryer dehydrates food more quickly than other types of dryers while producing improved-quality desiccated food [126]–[129]. Hawlader et al.'s [130] evaluation of a sun dryer combined with a heat engine and water heater in tropic meteorological conditions. The dryer's efficiency affected the airflow rate, temperature, solar energy, relative humidity, compressor speed, and weight inside the dehydrating compartment. Queiroz et al. [131] proved the dehydration of tomatoes using a heat pump dryer and an electric resistance dryer. 40% more energy was needed for the heat exchanger than for the electric dryer. The best model for explaining the drying behavior of tomatoes was found to be the Page equation. Prasad et al. [132] evaluated a combination dryer's efficacy for dehydrating turmeric. The dryer's effectiveness was 28.57% at the 55°C and 60°C air dehydrating temps.

An indirect solar dryer with combined solar collector storage and biomass backup warmers was developed and studied by Madhlopa and Ngwalo [130]. Three techniques, including solar, biomass, and solar biomass, were the subjects of the study. For solar dehydration, moisture collection had a 15% efficacy. For sun biomass and biomass modes, the effectiveness of moisture pickup was 13% and 11%, respectively. Experimental research on a combination forced-convection dryer was conducted. The hybrid dryer supplied heat to the dehydrating room, a sun collection, a biomass gasifier furnace, and a rock bed with a heat exchanger. Chili was dried using the dryer at a pace of 90 m³ per hour and a temperature of 60°C. T dehydrating heated air's temperature remained steady at 60 ± 3°C for about 21 hours [133]

Suherman et al.'s [33] investigation of a combination dryer's efficiency for cassava flour. The hybrid drying device with a dehydrating compartment, an exhaust blower, and a collector is shown in Fig. 1(g). Liquefied petroleum gas was used with the sun dryer as a supplemental heater to aid in drying. A rehydration trial started at ten in the morning. temps of the dryer air were 40°C, 50°C, and 60°C from noon to one o'clock. The researchers discovered that the sampling period and atmospheric conditions significantly impacted air temperature, solar radiation, and relative humidity. Dehydration was fast and efficient due to the hot air. The first container experienced the fastest drop in moisture level, followed by the second and third trays. The main part of the dehydration process was swiftly completed during the constant-rate time in this process. The drying of cassava starch typically takes place during the falling-rate phase.

Solar dryer	Advantage	Disadvantage	References
Direct	Simple construction, easy loading and unloading, dryer made to withstand rain and dust, and the ability to put food items in the dryer at night or in the rain.	Unskilled consumers inspect the desiccated product quality in low-capacity quantities of about (2–10 kg).	[1]
Primarily, Solar energy is			

		to blame. Food discoloration is surmounted, and the cooling rate is influenced mainly by temperature.	
Indirect	Due to the straight dryer, the dehydrating rate is greater. Decent dehydrating efficiency, high-quality dehydrating foodstuffs, reserves flat plate solar collection was run and produced a decent outcome are all accessible to small farms.	The expensive initial expense of about USD 220.	[1]
Mixed-mode	The solar collection and dehydrating container receive sun energy incident on them. This drier, used to dehydrate crops, offers an adequate outcome for the most astounding dehydrating efficiency and moisture content. The drying rate was the highest.	The significant upfront expense of about \$900.	[1]
Hybrid	This dryer can operate without sunlight, reduce food waste, and dry items more quickly than natural and forced convection dryers while maintaining consistent temperature and moisture levels.	6000 US dollars or more in cost, including gasoline and petrol.	[1]

Table 9: Advantage and disadvantage of several solar dryers

7. Electrohydrodynamic (EHD)

EHD is frequently called the research of charged objects like ions or plasma. Electrical wind, corona discharge, ionic current, and electrical radiation are other terms in the literature [134]. Due to its low energy consumption, non-mechanical design, simplicity, and quick control, this method is preferable to others [135], [136]. The EHD method also improves the electric field and fluid interplay, increasing the heat and mass transmission coefficient [34] **Fig. 1(h)** [134], [137] shows the system that produces the high-voltage electric field, which is composed of different electrode configurations (needle or wire) and one plate electrode.

8. EHD applications in drying

In the food industry, the EHD principle can be applied to reduce the respiration rate, increase the freezing and thawing rate, enhance the drying process's efficiency, and improve microorganism removal efficiency [135], [138]–[140]. EHD drying is a significant non-thermal food processing method that has recently attracting much attention. Compared to conventional drying systems, it effectively addresses both concerns of high product quality and low energy consumption [136], [141], [142]. The saturated air layer, which forms the boundary between the air and the food surface, can be disturbed by the EHD drying method, which can also increase evaporation rates and mass transfer coefficients [136], [137]. Due to the altered material entropy, EHD can lower the drying temperature without affecting the kinetics of the process. Therefore, this drying technique appeals to heat-sensitive materials like food and pharmaceuticals [136]. EHD drying is also distinguished by having a relatively low energy requirement, particularly when compared to traditional water removal techniques.

According to [143] estimates, depending on the moisture content of the product, the specific energy consumption of convection drying ranges from 3900 to 5000 kJ/kg, while that of EHD drying ranges between 520 and 1670 kJ/kg. The authors of other works emphasize that industrial convective belt dryers have an energy efficiency of ca. 3800-3950 kJ/kg, indicating that EHD dryers still perform better in energy efficiency [144]. It can be seen from an analysis of the energy effectiveness of EHD drying that the specific energy required for water removal is even less than the latent heat needed for water vaporization. Naturally, this situation is connected to the EHD mechanism, which removes water from the material [145]. Yang, Ding, and Zhu investigated the impact of two levels of electric field intensity and five levels of the gap on the energy consumption and drying characteristics of Chinese wolfberry fruits using the EHD drying method [146]. Their findings demonstrated that, compared to oven drying, the EHD drying system could increase the polysaccharide content, energy consumption, and drying rate [146].

9. Pulsed electric field-PEF

Non-thermal technology, known as a pulsed electric field (PEF), is dependent on the application of brief pulses that have a very high amplitude of electric field strength to food between two electrodes [147]–[150]

PEF applications in drying

Dehydration is one of food technology's most common and energy-consuming unit operations. This is because most drying systems have cellular structures, and later evaporation has a high latent heat of vaporization [151], [152]. The cellular makeup of the food significantly impacts the second stage of drying. Electroporation can accelerate water transfer from the tissue to the environment because it causes the cellular structure of the tissue food system to degrade. The drying time cut by PEF pretreatment depends on the raw material, drying method, and applied parameters. Electroporation's effectiveness depends on several processing-related parameters, and there is no standard PEF application method, making it challenging to compare the findings reported by various research groups. However, electric field strength and energy input are the essential PEF treatment parameters. The cell disintegration index, which ranges from 0 (for untreated material) to 1 (for electroporation effectiveness), can be used to assess the procedure's efficacy. (For hypothetical material with destroyed cellular structure). According to reports, applying PEF before air drying can reduce drying time for apple tissue and, respectively, okra by 2 to 50%, depending on the raw material [153], [154]. According to recently published articles, drying time for plant raw materials that have been PEF treated before

drying is reduced by, on average, 13–30% compared to untreated material [155]–[157]. While some crucial characteristics of dried goods, like rehydration, don't change, others, like color. Such actions are connected to the electroporation phenomenon, which causes cell fluid to leak into the extracellular environment. The enzymatic set is impacted by some food matrices' PEF color and bioactive qualities, but some food matrices may be preserved due to some microstructure changes.

According to reports, untreated material bleached out, while air-dried carrots that had been pretreated before dehydrated by PEF maintained their orange color [155]. According to a study, carrots pretreated with combined PEF and sonication before being air-dried had a higher content of carotenoids than the reference samples [156]. Energy consumption, significantly less than the energy required for water evaporation, is one of PEF treatment's main advantages in drying or freeze-drying intensification. Typically, 0.5 to 100 kJ/kg of energy is required to perform electroporation at a level high enough to improve drying [155]. The fact that PEF treatment qualifies as a volumetric method is another benefit of the procedure. The need for material and drying method optimization is the main issue that needs to be dealt with during industrialization. Additionally, in some circumstances, after adding PEF to the technological regime, the drying protocol needs to be adjusted to reap the benefits of pretreatment.

10. Ultrasound

High-intensity Ultrasound is a technology used in the food industry because it is considered safe, non-toxic, and environmentally friendly. Waves and mechanical vibrations with frequencies higher than those audible to humans are the foundation of ultrasound [158]

10.1 High Frequency-Ultrasound

Firmness, sugar content, and other physicochemical aspects of food, to name just a few, can be determined using low energy (high frequency) ultrasound waves as an analytical method for non-destructive quality and process inspection [35], [159].

10.2 Low Frequency-Ultrasound

High-energy (low-frequency) ultrasound is frequently applied as a pretreatment or food processing technique to enhance the primary process [35], [159]. The bubbles' formation, growth, and collapse during ultrasound treatment release the energy absorbed, which may contribute to physicochemical changes [35], [36].

10.3 Ultrasound applications in drying

Ultrasound in food product drying has grown in popularity in recent years. One of the cutting-edge technologies that are frequently used in conjunction with displacement dryers is ultrasound, which is primarily used to speed up processing and enhance product quality [135], [160]–[162]. Other benefits of using ultrasound include faster drying times and reduced need for high temperatures. Consequently, without adverse effects on the dried product's quality, the ultrasound system can be used as a pretreatment or combined with other drying heat-sensitive food products [163]. Research has shown that ultrasound reduced shrinkage and improved the dried product's color and sensory properties by increasing the significant moisture diffusion coefficient and the water diffusion rate during drying. One of the issues with dried food is water reabsorption. Ultrasound in food product drying can enhance water absorption by indicating internal stresses and tiny pores inside [135], [164].

Model Name	Model	Reference
Page	$MR = \exp(-Kt^N)$	[165]
Hii <i>et al.</i>	$MR = A \exp(-K_1t^N) + B \exp(-K_2t^N)$	[166]
Midilli-Kucuk	$MR = A \exp(-K_1t^N) + Bt$	[167]

Verma	$MR = A \exp(-K_1t) + (1-A) \exp(-K_2t)$	[168]
Modified Page	$MR = \exp\left(-K_1t^N \exp\left(-\frac{A}{T_k}\right)\right)$	[169]
Modified two component	$MR = A_1 \exp\left(-K_1t \exp\left(-\frac{B}{T_k}\right)\right) + A_2 \exp\left(-K_2t \exp\left(-\frac{B}{T_k}\right)\right)$	[169]
Newton	$MR = \exp(-kt)$	[170]
Henderson & Pabis	$MR = A \exp(-Kt)$	[171]

Table 10: Most common drying model found in literature

Conclusion

Traditional food drying techniques, such as sun and other drying techniques, have been utilized since ancient times. Modern drying procedures have been developed to reduce the damage caused by metabolic changes that degrade nutritional value throughout the drying process. Sun drying, tunnel drying, spray drying, drum drying, freezing, microwave drying, and fluidized bed drying are some of the most prevalent food drying procedures. In this review paper, the impact of pretreatments on solar dryers, greenhouse solar dryers, hybrid solar dryers, electro-hydrodynamic (EHD), pulsed electric field (PEF), and ultrasound are discussed, as are the working principles of model drying, impingement drying, high electric field drying, and electrode hydrodynamic drying. This study will examine food processing technologies' most contemporary drying processes.

Author Contributions: **Shamim Hossan:** Writing-original draft, Conceptualization, Investigation, Review and Editing; **Sazzadul Wasim:** Review and Editing- figures; **Mst Nushrat Yiasmin:** Review and Editing; **Md. Nazmus Saqib:** Review and Editing; **Md. Easdani:** Review and Editing; **Siyuan Liu:** Review and Editing.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] H. S. EL-Mesery, A. I. EL-Seesy, Z. Hu, and Y. Li, "Recent developments in solar drying technology of food and agricultural products: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 157. Elsevier Ltd, Apr. 01, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2021.112070.
- [2] J. S. H. C. P. G. A. A. H. K. Naseer Ahmed *, "Different Drying Methods: Their Applications and Recent Advances," *International Journal of Food Nutrition and Safety*, 2013, 4(1): 34-42, Journal homepage: www.ModernScientificPress.com/Journals/IJFNS.aspx, 2013.
- [3] H. Essalhi, M. Benchrifa, R. Tadili, and M. N. Bargach, "Experimental and theoretical analysis of drying grapes under an indirect solar dryer and in open sun," *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, vol. 49, pp. 58–64, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.IFSET.2018.08.002.

- [4] A. H. A. F. C. A. A. G. A. A. S. R. A. Rossi Indiarto, "Conventional And Advanced Food-Drying Technology: A Current Review," *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH VOLUME 10, ISSUE 01, JANUARY*, 2021.
- [5] R. Najjar and C. Stubenrauch, "Phase diagrams of microemulsions containing reducing agents and metal salts as bases for the synthesis of metallic nanoparticles," *J Colloid Interface Sci*, vol. 331, no. 1, pp. 214–220, Mar. 2009, doi: 10.1016/J.JCIS.2008.11.035.
- [6] A. K. Datta, "Heat and mass transfer in the microwave processing of food—Heat and mass transfer in the microwave processing of food," *Chem. Eng. Prog.*, vol. 86, no. 6, pp. 47–53, 1990.
- [7] M. A. Z. and M. A.-Z. A. Zubaidi, "Experimental Evaluation of Apple Drying Process In A Fluidized Bed Dryer," *Int. J. Environ. Agric. Sci.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–7, 2018.
- [8] P. Udomkun et al., "Review of solar dryers for agricultural products in Asia and Africa: An innovation landscape approach," *J Environ Manage*, vol. 268, p. 110730, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110730.
- [9] M. S. ed. Rahman, "Handbook of Food Preservation (2nd ed.). Boca Raton: CRC Press. ISBN 9781420017373,," 2007.
- [10] R. P. F. Guiné, "The Drying of Foods and Its Effect on the Physical-Chemical, Sensorial and Nutritional Properties," *ETP International Journal of Food Engineering*, pp. 93–100, 2018, doi: 10.18178/ijfe.4.2.93-100.
- [11] A. F. K. Correia, A. C. Loro, S. Zanatta, M. H. F. Spoto, and T. M. F. S. Vieira, "Effect of temperature, time, and material thickness on the dehydration process of tomato," *Int J Food Sci*, vol. 2015, 2015, doi: 10.1155/2015/970724.
- [12] S. V. R. Suresh Kumar, "Recent advances in drying and dehydration of fruits and vegetables: a review," 2009.
- [13] T. Y. Tunde-Akintunde, T. J. Afolabi, and B. O. Akintunde, "Influence of drying methods on drying of bell-pepper (*Capsicum annuum*)," *J Food Eng*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 439–442, Jun. 2005, doi: 10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2004.06.021.
- [14] P. B. Imoudu and A. A. Olufayo, "The effect of sun-drying on milling yield and quality of rice," *Bioresour Technol*, vol. 74, no. 3, pp. 267–269, Sep. 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0960-8524(99)00128-5.
- [15] R. R. Milczarek, J. J. Ferry, F. S. Alleyne, C. W. Olsen, D. A. Olson, and R. Winston, "Solar thermal drum drying performance of prune and tomato pomaces," *Food and Bioproducts Processing*, vol. 106, pp. 53–64, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.FBP.2017.08.009.
- [16] C. Henríquez, A. Córdova, S. Almonacid, and J. Saavedra, "Kinetic modeling of phenolic compound degradation during drum-drying of apple peel by-products," *J Food Eng*, vol. 143, pp. 146–153, Dec. 2014, doi: 10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2014.06.037.
- [17] J. A. Hernández Becerra, A. A. Ochoa Flores, G. Valerio-Alfaro, I. Soto-Rodríguez, M. T. Rodríguez-Estrada, and H. S. García, "Cholesterol oxidation and astaxanthin degradation in shrimp during sun drying and storage," *Food Chem*, vol. 145, pp. 832–839, Feb. 2014, doi: 10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2013.08.098.
- [18] K. Kumakura et al., "Nutritional content and health benefits of sun-dried and salt-aged radish (takuan-zuke)," *Food Chem*, vol. 231, pp. 33–41, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2017.03.096.
- [19] D. K. Youn, H. K. No, and W. Prinyawiwatkul, "Physicochemical and functional properties of chitosans affected by sun drying time during decoloration," *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, vol. 42, no. 9, pp. 1553–1556, Nov. 2009, doi: 10.1016/J.LWT.2009.05.004.
- [20] P. J. Cáceres, E. Peñas, C. Martínez-Villaluenga, L. Amigo, and J. Frias, "Enhancement of biologically active compounds in germinated brown rice and the effect of sun-drying," *J Cereal Sci*, vol. 73, pp. 1–9, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.JCS.2016.11.001.
- [21] N. R. Pochont, M. N. Mohammad, B. T. Pradeep, and P. Vijaya Kumar, "A comparative study of drying kinetics and quality of Indian red chilli in solar hybrid greenhouse drying and open sun drying," *Mater Today Proc*, vol. 21, pp. 286–290, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.MATPR.2019.05.433.

- [22] B. K. Bala and M. R. A. Mondol, "EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON SOLAR DRYING OF FISH USING SOLAR TUNNEL DRYER," *Drying Technology*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 427–436, Feb. 2001, doi: 10.1081/DRT-100102915.
- [23] V. G. and A. S. —A R. on S. D. T. and S. G. D. iosr jmce, vol. 13, pp. 31–37, Jun. 2016. T. Sahu, "A Review on Solar Drying Techniques and Solar Greenhouse Dryer," 2016.
- [24] N. S. Rathore and N. L. Panwar, "Experimental studies on hemi cylindrical walk-in type solar tunnel dryer for grape drying," *Appl Energy*, vol. 87, no. 8, pp. 2764–2767, Aug. 2010, doi: 10.1016/J.APENERGY.2010.03.014.
- [25] S. P. R. and A. V. 2320 – 7051 *Int. J. P. App. Biosci.* 6 (2): 1368-1373 (2018), DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.18782/2320-7051.2916> v. Arun Prasath^{1*}, "Development of Solar Tunnel Dryer for Drying Tomato (*Lycopersicum esculentum*) Slices," 2018.
- [26] M. A. Hossain and B. K. Bala, "Drying of hot chilli using solar tunnel drier," *Solar Energy*, vol. 81, no. 1, pp. 85–92, Jan. 2007, doi: 10.1016/J.SOLENER.2006.06.008.
- [27] M. S. P. studies of solar tunnel dryer for drying aonla (*embilica officinalis*) pulp. *Appl. Sol. E.* 48, 104–111 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.3103/S0003701X12020181> Seveda, "Performance studies of solar tunnel dryer for drying aonla (*embilica officinalis*) pulp," 2012.
- [28] N. L. , R. N. S. & W. N. T. M. and E. V. of a W. T. S. T. D. for D. F. L. (Methi) in *I. Climate. E. M. A.* 20, 211–223 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10666-014-9427-1> Panwar, "Thermal Modelling and Experimental Validation of a Walk-in Type Solar Tunnel Dryer for Drying Fenugreek Leaves (Methi) in Indian Climate," 2015.
- [29] U. of Z. P. O. B. 32379, L. Z. Isaac Nyambe Simate 1 and Sam Cherotich 1 ¹Department of Agricultural Engineering, "Design and Testing of a Natural Convection Solar Tunnel Dryer for Mango," 2017.
- [30] H. Hallak, J. Hilal, F. Hilal, and R. Rahhal, "The staircase solar dryer: Design and characteristics," *Renew Energy*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 177–183, Feb. 1996, doi: 10.1016/0960-1481(95)00127-1.
- [31] K. S. Exell RHB, "A low-cost solar rice dryer. *Appropr Technol* 1978."
- [32] J. L. B. C.B. Pardhi, "Development and performance evaluation of mixed-mode solar dryer with forced convection. *Int J Energy Environ Eng* 4, 23 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1186/2251-6832-4-23>," 2013.
- [33] S. E. Z. A. D. NHR. Suherman S, "Performance study of hybrid solar dryer for cassava starch. In: *AIP Conf. Proc.*, vol. 2197. AIP Publishing LLC; 2020. p. 80003," 2020.
- [34] A. Mousakhani-Ganjeh et al., "Electro-based technologies in food drying - A comprehensive review," *LWT*, vol. 145. Academic Press, Jun. 01, 2021. doi: 10.1016/j.lwt.2021.111315.
- [35] A. Amiri, A. Mousakhani-Ganjeh, S. Torbati, G. Ghaffarinejhad, and R. Esmailzadeh Kenari, "Impact of high-intensity ultrasound duration and intensity on the structural properties of whipped cream," *Int Dairy J*, vol. 78, pp. 152–158, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.IDAIRYJ.2017.12.002.
- [36] A. Amiri, P. Sharifian, and N. Soltanizadeh, "Application of ultrasound treatment for improving the physicochemical, functional and rheological properties of myofibrillar proteins," *Int J Biol Macromol*, vol. 111, pp. 139–147, May 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.IJBIOMAC.2017.12.167.
- [37] L. Liu, X. Dai, H. Kang, Y. Xu, and W. Hao, "Structural and functional properties of hydrolyzed/glycosylated ovalbumin under spray drying and microwave freeze drying," *Food Science and Human Wellness*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 80–87, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.FSHW.2020.01.003.
- [38] B. A. R. M. I. R. upm. edu. my:8080/dspace/handle/0/12735 Nurhadi, "Study the properties of honey powder produced from spray drying and vacuum drying method," 2012.
- [39] S. B. Araujo-Díaz, C. Leyva-Porras, P. Aguirre-Bañuelos, C. Álvarez-Salas, and Z. Saavedra-Leos, "Evaluation of the physical properties and conservation of the antioxidants content, employing inulin and maltodextrin in the spray drying of blueberry juice," *Carbohydr Polym*, vol. 167, pp. 317–325, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.CARBPOL.2017.03.065.

- [40] J. A. Pellicer, M. I. Fortea, J. Trabal, M. I. Rodríguez-López, J. A. Gabaldón, and E. Núñez-Delicado, "Stability of microencapsulated strawberry flavour by spray drying, freeze drying and fluid bed," *Powder Technol*, vol. 347, pp. 179–185, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.POWTEC.2019.03.010.
- [41] F. P. Chen, L. L. Liu, and C. H. Tang, "Spray-drying microencapsulation of curcumin nanocomplexes with soy protein isolate: Encapsulation, water dispersion, bioaccessibility and bioactivities of curcumin," *Food Hydrocoll*, vol. 105, p. 105821, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2020.105821.
- [42] J. Guo, P. Li, L. Kong, and B. Xu, "Microencapsulation of curcumin by spray drying and freeze drying," *LWT*, vol. 132, p. 109892, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.LWT.2020.109892.
- [43] C. Encina, G. Márquez-Ruiz, F. Holgado, B. Giménez, C. Vergara, and P. Robert, "Effect of spray-drying with organic solvents on the encapsulation, release and stability of fish oil," *Food Chem*, vol. 263, pp. 283–291, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2018.05.026.
- [44] H. M. Lisboa, M. E. Duarte, and M. E. Cavalcanti-Mata, "Modeling of food drying processes in industrial spray dryers," *Food and Bioproducts Processing*, vol. 107, pp. 49–60, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.FBP.2017.09.006.
- [45] J. Lucas, M. Ralaivao, B. N. Estevinho, and F. Rocha, "A new approach for the microencapsulation of curcumin by a spray drying method, in order to value food products," *Powder Technol*, vol. 362, pp. 428–435, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.POWTEC.2019.11.095.
- [46] A. H. A. F. C. A. A. G. A. A. S. R. A. Rossi Indiarto, "Conventional And Advanced Food-Drying Technology: A Current Review Article in," *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, vol. 10, p. 1, 2021, [Online]. Available: www.ijstr.org
- [47] K. Aalaei, M. Rayner, and I. Sjöholm, "Storage stability of freeze-dried, spray-dried and drum-dried skim milk powders evaluated by available lysine," *LWT*, vol. 73, pp. 675–682, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1016/J.LWT.2016.07.011.
- [48] P. Galaz, M. Valdenegro, C. Ramírez, H. Nuñez, S. Almonacid, and R. Simpson, "Effect of drum drying temperature on drying kinetic and polyphenol contents in pomegranate peel," *J Food Eng*, vol. 208, pp. 19–27, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2017.04.002.
- [49] P. Wiriyawattana, S. Suwonsichon, and T. Suwonsichon, "Effects of drum drying on physical and antioxidant properties of riceberry flour," *Agriculture and Natural Resources*, vol. 52, no. 5, pp. 445–450, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.ANRES.2018.11.008.
- [50] S. Elmholt, E. F. Kristensen, and U. Thrane, "Comparing the effect of continuous drying and drum drying on fungal contamination of bread grain (rye)," *Biosyst Eng*, vol. 97, no. 3, pp. 425–428, Jul. 2007, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOSYSTEMSENG.2007.03.017.
- [51] K. Sakulnarmrat, D. Wongsrikaew, and I. Konczak, "Microencapsulation of red cabbage anthocyanin-rich extract by drum drying technique," *LWT*, vol. 137, p. 110473, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.LWT.2020.110473.
- [52] C. K. Pua, N. S. A. Hamid, C. P. Tan, H. Mirhosseini, R. B. A. Rahman, and G. Rusul, "Optimization of drum drying processing parameters for production of jackfruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*) powder using response surface methodology," *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. 343–349, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.1016/J.LWT.2009.08.011.
- [53] C. K. Pua, N. S. A. Hamid, G. Rusul, and R. A. Rahman, "Production of drum-dried jackfruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*) powder with different concentration of soy lecithin and gum arabic," *J Food Eng*, vol. 78, no. 2, pp. 630–636, Jan. 2007, doi: 10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2005.10.041.
- [54] R. H. , D. H. & A. S. Kakade, "Performance evaluation of a double drum dryer for potato flake production. *J Food Sci Technol* 48, 432–439 (2011).," 2011.
- [55] D. , & P. P. B. Jain, "Study the drying kinetics of open sun drying of fish. *Journal of food Engineering*, 78(4), 1315-1319.," 2007.

- [56] R. G. C. O. V. A. and S. R. Gharsallaoui A, "Applications of spray-drying in microencapsulation of food ingredients: an overview. *Food Res. Intl.* 40, 1107–1121,," 2007.
- [57] Katta S and Gauvin W, "Basic concepts of spray dryer design. *AICHE J.* 22 (4), 713–724," 1976.
- [58] D. R. H. S. . R Paul Singh, "Introduction to Food Engineering (5th ed.). Academic Press. ISBN: 9780124016750. Tunnel Dryer 683-684 page," 2013.
- [59] N. , H. M. A. A. M. M. Kasiri, "Mathematical modelling and computer simulation of a drum dryer, *Iranian Journal of scinec and technology*, 28(6):679 – 687," 2004.
- [60] F. H. and S. G. Tang J., "Drum Drying in *Encyclopedia of Agricultural, Food, and Biological Engineering* by Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York," 2010.
- [61] S. , K. R. , H. M. , S. K. and C. S. R. Khairmar, "A review on freeze drying process of pharmaceuticals, *International Journal of research in pharmacy and science*, 4(1):76 – 94," 2013.
- [62] G. G. S. , N. K. V. and G. H. V. Harish, "Lyophilization – The process and industrial use, *International Journal of universal pharmacy and biosciences*, 6(2):198 – 205," 2017.
- [63] K. , M. K. and U. M. R. V. Rajeevini, "Review on Lyophilization technique, *International Journal of trends in pharmacy and life sciences*, 1(1):130 – 140," 2015.
- [64] Y. Huang, "Impact of Banana (*Musa acuminata*) ripening on resistant and non-resistant starch using hot-air and microwave drying, A thesis at Department of Bioresource Engineering, McGill University, Montreal, Canada," 2013.
- [65] A. , S. O. and K. M. Balbay, "An investigation of drying process of shelled pistachio in a newly designed fixed bed dryer system by artificial neural network, *Drying technology*, 28: 1685 – 1696," 2011.
- [66] V. K. , T. A. , G. J. , P. M. C. and R. k. Shiby, "Effect of drying methods on moisture sorption, microstructure and other quality characteristics of chicken cubes, *International Journal of advanced research*, 3(12):1200 – 1213," 2015.
- [67] Mujumdar A S and Devahastin S, "Applications for fluidized bed drying In ed W. C. Yang, *Handbook of fluidization and fluid particle systems* (New York: Marcel Dekker) p 469-84," 2003.
- [68] A. I. L. O. K. C. H. Sadikoglu, "OPTIMAL CONTROL OF THE PRIMARY AND SECONDARY DRYING STAGES OF BULK SOLUTION FREEZE DRYING IN TRAYS," 2007.
- [69] A. I. Liapis and R. Bruttini, "A theory for the primary and secondary drying stages of the freeze-drying of pharmaceutical crystalline and amorphous solutes: comparison between experimental data and theory," *Separations Technology*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 144–155, Jul. 1994, doi: 10.1016/0956-9618(94)80017-0.
- [70] M. O. M. S. H. Sadikoglu, "Optimal Control of the Primary Drying Stage of Freeze Drying of Solutions in Vials Using Variational Calculus," Taylor & Francis Online, 2007.
- [71] W. Wang, M. Chen, and G. Chen, "Issues in Freeze Drying of Aqueous Solutions," *Chin J Chem Eng*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 551–559, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1016/S1004-9541(11)60218-8.
- [72] X. Y. G. R. Y. P. Xu Duan, "Technical aspects in freeze-drying of foods," Tailor & Francis Online, 2016.
- [73] A. S. and R. S. Navin Chandra Shahi, "Optimization of Freeze-Drying Process Parameters for Qualitative Evaluation of Button Mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) Using Response Surface Methodology," 2017.
- [74] K. J. E. P. Kouamé, A. F. M. Bora, X. Li, Y. Sun, and L. Liu, "Novel trends and opportunities for microencapsulation of flaxseed oil in foods: A review," *J Funct Foods*, vol. 87, p. 104812, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.JFF.2021.104812.
- [75] C. Chi et al., "Understanding the effect of freeze-drying on microstructures of starch hydrogels," *Food Hydrocoll*, vol. 101, p. 105509, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2019.105509.
- [76] J. B. G. Konstantinos Papoutsis, "Encapsulation of Citrus By-Product Extracts by Spray-Drying and Freeze-Drying Using Combinations of Maltodextrin with Soybean Protein and ι -Carrageenan," 2018.

- [77] Y. Feng et al., "Effect of freeze-thaw cycles pretreatment on the vacuum freeze-drying process and physicochemical properties of the dried garlic slices," *Food Chem*, vol. 324, p. 126883, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2020.126883.
- [78] H. F. and M. L. J. Tang, "Microwave heating in food processing. Singapore: World Scientific," 2002.
- [79] Chaowalit Monton, "Convection combined microwave drying affect quality of volatile oil compositions and quantity of curcuminoids of turmeric raw material," 2019.
- [80] L. Valadez-Carmona et al., "Effects of microwaves, hot air and freeze-drying on the phenolic compounds, antioxidant capacity, enzyme activity and microstructure of cacao pod husks (*Theobroma cacao* L.)," *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, vol. 41, pp. 378–386, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.IFSET.2017.04.012.
- [81] I. Staniszevska et al., "Microwave-assisted hot air convective drying of whole cranberries subjected to various initial treatments," *LWT*, vol. 133, p. 109906, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.LWT.2020.109906.
- [82] Y. Jia et al., "Influence of three different drying techniques on persimmon chips' characteristics: A comparison study among hot-air, combined hot-air-microwave, and vacuum-freeze drying techniques," *Food and Bioproducts Processing*, vol. 118, pp. 67–76, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.FBP.2019.08.018.
- [83] J. Li, Z. Li, L. Li, C. Song, G. S. V. Raghavan, and F. He, "Microwave drying of balsam pear with online aroma detection and control," *J Food Eng*, vol. 288, p. 110139, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2020.110139.
- [84] S. P. P. Sutar, "Microwave drying technology-recent developments and R&D needs in India," *Proc. 42nd ISAE Annu. Conv.*, pp. 1–3," 2008.
- [85] R. L. Monteiro, B. A. M. Carciofi, and J. B. Laurindo, "A microwave multi-flash drying process for producing crispy bananas," *J Food Eng*, vol. 178, pp. 1–11, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2015.12.024.
- [86] F. I. S. E. and H. Y. T. Baysal, "Effects of microwave and infrared drying on the quality of carrot and garlic," *Eur. Food Res. Technol.*, vol. 218, no. 1, pp. 68–73," 2003.
- [87] M. Amer, M. Nour, M. Ahmed, S. Ookawara, S. Nada, and A. Elwardany, "The effect of microwave drying pretreatment on dry torrefaction of agricultural biomasses," *Bioresour Technol*, vol. 286, p. 121400, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.BIORTECH.2019.121400.
- [88] N. A. A. H. N. and L. B. M. Djaeni, "Corn Drying with Zeolite in The Fluidized Bed Dryer under Medium Temperature," *IPTEK J. Technol. Sci.*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 13–18," 2013.
- [89] T. Nazghelichi, M. H. Kianmehr, and M. Aghbashlo, "Thermodynamic analysis of fluidized bed drying of carrot cubes," *Energy*, vol. 35, no. 12, pp. 4679–4684, Dec. 2010, doi: 10.1016/J.ENERGY.2010.09.036.
- [90] M. Khanali, A. Khakpour Giglou, and S. Rafiee, "Model development for shelled corn drying in a plug flow fluidized bed dryer," *Engineering in Agriculture, Environment and Food*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1–8, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.EAEF.2017.09.002.
- [91] H. Darvishi, M. H. Khoshtaghaza, and S. Minaei, "Effects of fluidized bed drying on the quality of soybean kernels," *Journal of the Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 134–139, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.1016/J.JSSAS.2013.09.002.
- [92] X. Zhu, Z. Zhang, L. M. Hinds, D. W. Sun, and B. K. Tiwari, "Applications of ultrasound to enhance fluidized bed drying of *Ascophyllum Nodosum*: Drying kinetics and product quality assessment," *Ultrason Sonochem*, vol. 70, p. 105298, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.ULTSONCH.2020.105298.
- [93] Supawan Tirawanichakul, "Effect of Fluidized Bed Drying Temperature on Various Quality Attributes of Paddy," 2007.
- [94] Siti Masrinda Tasirin, "Drying of *Citrus sinensis* Peels in an Inert Fluidized Bed: Kinetics, Microbiological Activity, Vitamin C, and Limonene Determination," 2014.

- [95] A. A. Ananno, M. H. Masud, P. Dabnichki, and A. Ahmed, "Design and numerical analysis of a hybrid geothermal PCM flat plate solar collector dryer for developing countries," *Solar Energy*, vol. 196, pp. 270–286, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.SOLENER.2019.11.069.
- [96] R. M. S. Ashish Agrawal, "A review of research and development work on solar dryers with heat storage," 2014.
- [97] B. M. A. Amer, M. A. Hossain, and K. Gottschalk, "Design and performance evaluation of a new hybrid solar dryer for banana," *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 813–820, Apr. 2010, doi: 10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2009.11.016.
- [98] Mahendra Singh Seveda, "Design of a photovoltaic powered forced convection solar dryer in NEH region of India. *Int J Renew Energy Resour* 2013;3:906–12.," 2013.
- [99] W. B. Chaouch, A. Khellaf, A. Mediani, M. E. A. Slimani, A. Loumani, and A. Hamid, "Experimental investigation of an active direct and indirect solar dryer with sensible heat storage for camel meat drying in Saharan environment," *Solar Energy*, vol. 174, pp. 328–341, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.SOLENER.2018.09.037.
- [100] Vinay Narayan Hegde, "Design, fabrication and performance evaluation of solar dryer for banana," 2015.
- [101] V. T. Karathanos and V. G. Belessiotis, "Sun and artificial air drying kinetics of some agricultural products," *J Food Eng*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 35–46, Jan. 1997, doi: 10.1016/S0260-8774(96)00050-7.
- [102] P. Gbaha, H. Yobouet Andoh, J. Kouassi Saraka, B. Kaménan Koua, and S. Touré, "Experimental investigation of a solar dryer with natural convective heat flow," *Renew Energy*, vol. 32, no. 11, pp. 1817–1829, Sep. 2007, doi: 10.1016/J.RENENE.2006.10.011.
- [103] E. A. . AB Eke, "Natural convection mud type solar dryers for rural farmers. *Niger J Technol Dev* 2011;8:92–108.," 2011.
- [104] J. D. Seveda M. S., "Design and performance evaluation of solar dryer for drying of large cardamom (*Amomum subulatum*)," *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy*, 2012.
- [105] Ayyappan S. and Mayilsamy K., "Solar tunnel drier with thermal storage for drying of copra. *Int J Energy Technol Pol* 2012;8:3–13," 2012.
- [106] D. A. I. Adeyemo. Y Sanusi, "Comparative study of performance of open, direct and indirect solar dryer in drying tomatoes. *Int J Curr Eng Technol* 2013;3: 637–45.," 2013.
- [107] E. W. F. B. Tefera A, "Evaluation and demonstration of direct solar potato dryer. *Livest Res Rural Dev* ;25.," 2013.
- [108] Eke BA., "Development of small scale direct mode natural convection solar dryer for tomato, okra and carrot. *Int J Eng Technol* ;3. ," 2013.
- [109] M. A. Basunia and T. Abe, "Thin-layer solar drying characteristics of rough rice under natural convection," *J Food Eng*, vol. 47, no. 4, pp. 295–301, Mar. 2001, doi: 10.1016/S0260-8774(00)00133-3.
- [110] A. B. Lingayat, V. P. Chandramohan, V. R. K. Raju, and V. Meda, "A review on indirect type solar dryers for agricultural crops – Dryer setup, its performance, energy storage and important highlights," *Appl Energy*, vol. 258, p. 114005, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.APENERGY.2019.114005.
- [111] S. Nayak and G. N. Tiwari, "Energy and exergy analysis of photovoltaic/thermal integrated with a solar greenhouse," *Energy Build*, vol. 40, no. 11, pp. 2015–2021, Jan. 2008, doi: 10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2008.05.007.
- [112] A. A. El-Sebaili, S. Aboul-Enein, M. R. I. Ramadan, and H. G. El-Gohary, "Experimental investigation of an indirect type natural convection solar dryer," *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 43, no. 16, pp. 2251–2266, Nov. 2002, doi: 10.1016/S0196-8904(01)00152-2.
- [113] M. Goud, M. V. V. Reddy, C. V.P., and S. S., "A novel indirect solar dryer with inlet fans powered by solar PV panels: Drying kinetics of *Capsicum Annum* and *Abelmoschus esculentus* with dryer performance," *Solar Energy*, vol. 194, pp. 871–885, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.SOLENER.2019.11.031.

- [114] V. R. Mugi and V. P. Chandramohan, "Energy and exergy analysis of forced and natural convection indirect solar dryers: Estimation of exergy inflow, outflow, losses, exergy efficiencies and sustainability indicators from drying experiments," *J Clean Prod*, vol. 282, p. 124421, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2020.124421.
- [115] O. Prakash, V. Laguri, A. Pandey, A. Kumar, and A. Kumar, "Review on various modelling techniques for the solar dryers," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 62, pp. 396–417, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.1016/J.RSER.2016.04.028.
- [116] Z. A. Ghatrehsamani SH, "Impacts of drying air temperature, bed depth and air flow rate on walnut drying rate in an indirect solar dryer. *Int J Agric Sci ;4:253.*," 2012.
- [117] E. Baniasadi, S. Ranjbar, and O. Boostanipour, "Experimental investigation of the performance of a mixed-mode solar dryer with thermal energy storage," *Renew Energy*, vol. 112, pp. 143–150, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.RENENE.2017.05.043.
- [118] B. O. O. A. P. Bolaji, "Performance evaluation of a mixed-mode solar dryer. *AU J Technol 2008;11:225–31.*," *AU Journal of Technology*, 2008.
- [119] T. S. Wibulsawas P, "Comparative performance of a solar cabinet dryer. *Proc Work Fuel Power 1980:1–14.* ".
- [120] I. N. Simate, "Optimization of mixed-mode and indirect-mode natural convection solar dryers," *Renew Energy*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 435–453, Mar. 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0960-1481(02)00041-1.
- [121] A. Zomorodian, D. Zare, and H. Ghasemkhani, "Optimization and evaluation of a semi-continuous solar dryer for cereals (Rice, etc)," *Desalination*, vol. 209, no. 1–3, pp. 129–135, Apr. 2007, doi: 10.1016/J.DESAL.2007.04.021.
- [122] B. K. Huang and M. Toksoy, "Design and analysis of greenhouse solar systems in agricultural production," *Energy in Agriculture*, vol. 2, no. C, pp. 115–136, Jan. 1983, doi: 10.1016/0167-5826(83)90012-8.
- [123] K. V. B. BK. Janjai S, "Development, design, and performance of a PV- ventilated greenhouse dryer. *Int Energy J 2007;8.*," 2007.
- [124] V. P. Sethi and S. Arora, "Improvement in greenhouse solar drying using inclined north wall reflection," *Solar Energy*, vol. 83, no. 9, pp. 1472–1484, Sep. 2009, doi: 10.1016/J.SOLENER.2009.04.001.
- [125] B. A. A. E. O. FF. Adu EA, "Design, construction and performance evaluation of a solar agricultural drying tent. *Int J Eng Res Technol 2012;1:1–11.*," 2012.
- [126] A. Reyes, A. Mahn, and F. Vásquez, "Mushrooms dehydration in a hybrid-solar dryer, using a phase change material," *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 83, pp. 241–248, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2014.03.077.
- [127] L. S. M. B. L. Y. Hao W, "Mathematical modeling and performance analysis of a new hybrid solar dryer of lemon slices for controlling drying temperature. *Energies 2020;13:350.*," 2020.
- [128] B. K. Bala and J. L. Woods, "Simulation of the indirect natural convection solar drying of rough rice," *Solar Energy*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 259–266, Sep. 1994, doi: 10.1016/0038-092X(94)90632-7.
- [129] M. Esen, "Thermal performance of a solar-aided latent heat store used for space heating by heat pump," *Solar Energy*, vol. 69, no. 1, pp. 15–25, Jan. 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0038-092X(00)00015-3.
- [130] A. Madhlopa and G. Ngwalo, "Solar dryer with thermal storage and biomass-backup heater," *Solar Energy*, vol. 81, no. 4, pp. 449–462, Apr. 2007, doi: 10.1016/J.SOLENER.2006.08.008.
- [131] A. L. G. V. R. N. T. R. Queiroz, "Drying kinetics of tomato by using electric resistance and heat pump dryers. *Dry Technol 2004;22:1603–20.*," 2007.
- [132] J. Prasad, V. K. Vijay, G. N. Tiwari, and V. P. S. Sorayan, "Study on performance evaluation of hybrid drier for turmeric (*Curcuma longa L.*) drying at village scale," *J Food Eng*, vol. 75, no. 4, pp. 497–502, Aug. 2006, doi: 10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2005.04.061.
- [133] S. K. MA Leon, "Design and performance evaluation of a solar-assisted biomass drying system with thermal storage. *Dry Technol 2008;26:936–47.*," 2008.

- [134] J. Wang, T. Zhu, Y. xi Cai, J. fei Zhang, and J. bo Wang, "Review on the recent development of corona wind and its application in heat transfer enhancement," *Int J Heat Mass Transf*, vol. 152, p. 119545, May 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.IJHEATMASSTRANSFER.2020.119545.
- [135] J. , D. C. , Z. Y. , S. Z. , & X. W. Ni, "Influence of ultrasonic pretreatment on electrohydrodynamic drying process of goji berry. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*, Article e14600.," *Food Processing and preservation*, 2020.
- [136] T. , & M. A. Kudra, " Electrohydrodynamic drying: Theory and experimental validation. *Drying Technology*, 38(1-2), 168-175.," *Drying technology*, 2020.
- [137] A. , O. V. , & R. v. Singh, " A comprehensive review on electrohydrodynamic drying and high-voltage electric field in the context of food and bioprocessing. *Drying Technology*, 30(16), 1812-1820. ," 2012.
- [138] A. Esehaghbeygi, K. Pirnazari, and M. Sadeghi, "Quality assessment of electrohydrodynamic and microwave dehydrated banana slices," *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, vol. 55, no. 2, pp. 565-571, Mar. 2014, doi: 10.1016/J.LWT.2013.10.010.
- [139] A. Mousakhani-Ganjeh, N. Hamdami, and N. Soltanizadeh, "Impact of high voltage electric field thawing on the quality of frozen tuna fish (*Thunnus albacares*)," *J Food Eng*, vol. 156, pp. 39-44, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2015.02.004.
- [140] A. Mousakhani-Ganjeh, N. Hamdami, and N. Soltanizadeh, "Thawing of frozen tuna fish (*Thunnus albacares*) using still air method combined with a high voltage electrostatic field," *J Food Eng*, vol. 169, pp. 149-154, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2015.08.036.
- [141] A. Martynenko, T. Astatkie, and T. Defraeye, "The role of convection in electrohydrodynamic drying," *J Food Eng*, vol. 271, p. 109777, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2019.109777.
- [142] J. Ni, C. Ding, Y. Zhang, and Z. Song, "Impact of different pretreatment methods on drying characteristics and microstructure of goji berry under electrohydrodynamic (EHD) drying process," *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, vol. 61, p. 102318, May 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.IFSET.2020.102318.
- [143] A. , & Z. W. Martynenko, " Overview of EHD drying technology. 12th International Congress on Engineering and Food (ICEF, 12. ," 2015.
- [144] T. , & M. A. Kudra, " Energy aspects in electrohydrodynamic drying. *Drying Technology*, 33(13), 1534-1540.," *Drying technology*, 2015.
- [145] T. Anukiruthika, J. A. Moses, and C. Anandharamakrishnan, "Electrohydrodynamic drying of foods: Principle, applications, and prospects," *J Food Eng*, vol. 295, p. 110449, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2020.110449.
- [146] M. , D. C. , & Z. J. Yang, "The drying quality and energy consumption of Chinese wolfberry fruits under electrohydrodynamic system. *International Journal of Applied Electromagnetics and Mechanics*, 55(1), 101-112. ," *International Journal of Applied Electromagnetics and Mechanics*, 2017.
- [147] F. J. Barba et al., "Current applications and new opportunities for the use of pulsed electric fields in food science and industry," *Food Research International*, vol. 77, pp. 773-798, Nov. 2015, doi: 10.1016/J.FOODRES.2015.09.015.
- [148] B. Gómez et al., "Application of pulsed electric fields in meat and fish processing industries: An overview," *Food Research International*, vol. 123, pp. 95-105, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.FOODRES.2019.04.047.
- [149] A. M. Khaneghah, M. Gavahian, Q. Xia, G. I. Denoya, E. Roselloâ'-Soto, and F. J. Barba, "Effect of pulsed electric field on Maillard reaction and hydroxymethylfurfural production," *Pulsed Electric Fields to Obtain Healthier and Sustainable Food for Tomorrow*, pp. 129-140, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-816402-0.00006-9.
- [150] N. Pallareâ's, J. Tolosa, M. Gavahian, F. J. Barba, A. Mousavi-Khaneghah, and E. Ferrer, "The potential of pulsed electric fields to reduce pesticides and toxins," *Pulsed Electric Fields to Obtain Healthier and Sustainable Food for Tomorrow*, pp. 141-152, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-816402-0.00007-0.

- [151] S. , & K. R. Kaleemullah, " Latent heat of vaporization of moisture from red chillies. *International Journal of Food Properties*, 8(2), 199–205., " *Int J Food Prop*, 2005.
- [152] A. , & W.-R. D. Wiktor, " Pulsed electric fields as pretreatment for subsequent food process operations. *Handbook of Electroporation*, 1–6. ," 2017.
- [153] A. , G. T. , N. M. , & R. G. Adedeji, " Effect of pretreatments on drying characteristics of okra. *Drying Technology*, 26(10), 1251–1256. ," *Drying Technology*, 2008.
- [154] A. , I. M. , Sled 'z, M. , N. M. , C. T. , & W.-R. D. Wiktor, "Drying kinetics of apple tissue treated by pulsed electric field. *Drying Technology*, 31(1), 112–119. ," *Drying Technology*, 2013.
- [155] F. J. Barba et al., "Current applications and new opportunities for the use of pulsed electric fields in food science and industry," *Food Research International*, vol. 77, pp. 773–798, Nov. 2015, doi: 10.1016/J.FOODRES.2015.09.015.
- [156] A. Wiktor, M. Dadan, M. Nowacka, K. Rybak, and D. Witrowa-Rajchert, "The impact of combination of pulsed electric field and ultrasound treatment on air drying kinetics and quality of carrot tissue," *LWT*, vol. 110, pp. 71–79, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.LWT.2019.04.060.
- [157] A. Lammerskitten et al., "Impact of pulsed electric fields on physical properties of freeze-dried apple tissue," *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, vol. 57, p. 102211, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.IFSET.2019.102211.
- [158] R. Azizi and A. Farahnaky, "Ultrasound assisted cold gelation of kappa carrageenan dispersions," *Carbohydr Polym*, vol. 95, no. 1, pp. 522–529, Jun. 2013, doi: 10.1016/J.CARBPOL.2013.02.073.
- [159] S. M. , G. S. N. , S. M. , R. S. , & L. ópez-M. A. Alzamora, " Inactivation of microorganisms Ultrasound technologies for food and bioprocessing. Springer.," 2011.
- [160] J. , & P. A. Banaszak, " Influence of ultrasound drying on properties of dried apple crisps. In Paper presented at the proceedings of 5th European drying conference (Eurodrying'2015). Budapest, Hungary.," 2015.
- [161] A. M. , R. S. , & F. F. A. Galvão, " Kinetics of ultrasound pretreated apple cubes dried in fluidized bed dryer. *Drying Technology*, 38(10), 1367–1377," *Drying Technology*, 2020.
- [162] S. J. Kowalski, A. Pawłowski, J. Szadzińska, J. Lechtańska, and M. Stasiak, "High power airborne ultrasound assist in combined drying of raspberries," *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, vol. 34, pp. 225–233, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.1016/J.IFSET.2016.02.006.
- [163] O., Eim, V., Rossell o, C., Femenia, A., C´arcel, J. A., & Simal, S. Rodríguez, "Application of power ultrasound on the convective drying of fruits and vegetables: Effects on quality. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 99(2), 966, 966., " 2019.
- [164] X. Zhu, Z. Zhang, L. M. Hinds, D. W. Sun, and B. K. Tiwari, "Applications of ultrasound to enhance fluidized bed drying of *Ascophyllum Nodosum*: Drying kinetics and product quality assessment," *Ultrason Sonochem*, vol. 70, p. 105298, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.ULTSONCH.2020.105298.
- [165] V. T. and V. G. Belessiotis. Karathanos, "Application of a thin layer equation to drying data of fresh and semi-dried fruits. *J. Agric. Eng. Res.* 74: 355-361," 1999.
- [166] C. L. , C. L. L. and M. Cloke. Hii, "Modeling using a new thin layer drying model and product quality of cocoa. *J. Food Eng.* 90: 191-198., " 2009.
- [167] A. , K. H. , Midilli, "Mathematical Modeling of thin layer drying of pistachio by using solar energy. *Energy Conversion and Management.*, 44 (7): 1111-1122., " 2003.
- [168] L. R. , R. A. Bucklin. , J. B. E. and F. T. Wratten. Verma, "Effects of drying air parameters on rice drying models. *Trans. ASAE.* 28: 296-301., " 1985.
- [169] W. Jittanit, "Modeling of seed drying using a two-stage drying concept. PhD Thesis. University of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia., " 2007.
- [170] A. S. MUJUMDAR, "HaiuibookofIndusrrial Drying. Marcel Dekker, New York., " 1987.

[171] Q. L. J. B. ZHANG, "An optimisation of intermittent corn drying in a laboratory scale thin layer dryer. Drying Technol. 9, 383-395," 1991.